

Fixed Point Theorem For Non-Expansive Mapping in Partial b -Metric Space

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ABSTRACT

The goal is to develop a class of non-expensive mappings known as α_s -non-expensive mappings. These α_s -non-expensive mappings fully satisfied the generalized conditions of contraction. Some fixed-point theorems have been proved for newly developed α_s -non-expensive mappings in the environment of complete partial b -metric space. The generalization of proposed new study is proved as the new results generalizes the pre-existing results. For demonstration of main results, few examples are provided. The application of proposed work is elaborated by applying it to a boundary value problem where the existence of solution is shown.

Keywords: Fixed Points; Non-Expansive Mapping; Partial b -Metric Space

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1. Introduction

A self-map T on a metric space (X, d) is considered as a contractive map iff $d(T(h), T(t)) \leq kd(h, t)$ for every $h, t \in X$ and k is positive real number less than 1. This map is further known as Non-Expensive map if we place $k = 1$. There exists some quality work based on contractive and non-expensive maps where several generalized conditions have been developed for these maps. Some related work could be found in [2-4, 6-7, 15, 22]. The theory of b -metric space was developed by Bakhtin [1] in 1989,

whereas the study of fixed points of self-maps have been carried out by Czerwik [2] as he proved the fixed-point theorem in b -metric space. After this development of b -metric space, various researchers took interests in the theory of b -metric space which results in the development of some well-known fixed point theorems for single valued mapping as well as for multi valued mapping in the environment of b -metric space. Among these researchers, some renowned mathematicians are Parvaneh *et al* [18], Roshan *et al* [23], Kir and Kiziltunc [13] and Shatanawi *et al* [24]. Khamsi and Hussain uses the cone in b -metric space to develop some results for KKM mappings. Some further contribution to fixed point theorems and their related theory have been done by Jovanovic *et al* [10] and Hussain and Huang [8, 9] in the environment of b -metric space.

Usually the fixed point theorems like Banach fixed point theorems are valid in Hausdorff topologies. In [16], Matthews's, developed a generalized metric having symmetric property and declared it as a partial metric. Matthews works enables him to extend the Banach fixed point theorems to non-Hausdorff topologies and thus providing a new dimension. Matthews work was further extended by Matthews and Czerwik Shukla [25] as they developed a generalized form of partial metric space known as partial b -metric space.

Further, Matthews and Czerwik Shukla worked on famous fixed point theorems like Banach, Kannan and Chatterjee contraction theorems in the environment of complete partial b -metric space. Some recent contribution in complete partial b -metric space include the work of Mustafa *et al.* [17], Piri *et al* [19] and Latif *et al.* [14].

In 1969, the concept of multi valued mappings was introduced by Sam B Nadler Jr provided a space for the development of various fixed-point results in the environment of b -metric space as well as partial b -metric space. Further in 1995,

Some non-expensive type single valued mappings and non-expensive type multi valued mappings were introduced by M. Chandra. Inspired by the work developed in [5, 16, 27], this thesis is a contribution to the generalization of the work proposed in [5, 16, 27]. In our proposed theory, we not only generalize the existing concepts but also investigate the basic properties of the results and discussed some fixed points theorems of non-expensive type in multi valued mappings in b -metric space as well as partial b -metric space.

Definition:

Let (X, d_{pb}^s, c) be a partial b -metric space and let T be a mapping on X and α_s be mappings on $X \times X$. Then T is α_s -non-expensive map if for all $h, t \in X$ $\alpha_s(h, t) \geq s^2 \Rightarrow d_{pb}^s(T(h), T(t)) \leq d_{pb}^s(h, t)$

The following example illustrates the concept of α_s -non-expensive mapping.

Example:

Let $X = R$ be endowed with a partial b -metric space

$$d_{pb}^s(h, t) = \{(h \vee t)^2 + |h - t|^2\}$$

for all $h, t \in X$, define T on X as:

$$T(h) = \frac{h^2 + h}{2}$$

Define $\mathbb{Q}_4: X \times X \rightarrow R_0^+$ by:

$$\mathbb{Q}_4(h, t) = \{16 \text{ if } h \in [0,1] \text{ } 0 \text{ otherwise}\}$$

Let $h, t \in X$ such that $\mathbb{Q}_4(h, t) = 16$, Then $h, t \in [0,1]$, in this case we note that

$$\left(\frac{h^2 + h}{2} \vee \frac{t^2 + t}{2}\right) \leq (h \vee t)^2$$

and

$$\left| \frac{h^2+h}{2} - \frac{t^2+t}{2} \right| \leq |h - t|^2.$$

Thus

$$d_{pb}^s(T(h), T(t)) = (T(h) \vee T(t))^2 + |T(h) - T(t)|^2 \leq d_{pb}^s(h, t).$$

Hence T is an $\mathbb{Q}_s$ -non-expensive map, observes that T is not a non-expensive map. In fact, for $h = 1, t = 2$, we have

$$d_{pb}^s(T(1), T(2)) = 13 > d_{pb}^s(1, 2) = 5$$

Lemma:

Let (X, d_{pb}^s, c) be a partial b -metric space and T be a non-expensive map on X . If there exist $h_0 \in X$ and $\{h_n\}$ be the periodic iterative sequence with initial point h_0 , then the sequence $\left\{ \frac{d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1})}{d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) + 1} \right\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is non-increasing.

2. Results

The aim of this chapter is to generalize the results proposed in [27]. First, in the environment of partial b -metric space, we study some fixed point theorems for a class of single-valued mappings. Likewise, Banach contraction principle, some contractive mappings have been considered here from the class of non-expensive single-valued mappings. The generalization of these mappings has also been discussed.

Theorem:

Let (X, d_{pb}^s, c) be a complete partial b -metric space and let T and $\mathbb{Q}_s$ non-expensive and $\mathbb{Q}_s$ -orbital admissible mapping satisfying

$$d_{pb}^s(T(h), T(t)) \leq \left(\frac{d_{pb}^s(h, T(t)) + d_{pb}^s(t, T(h))}{c(d_{pb}^s(h, T(h)) + d_{pb}^s(t, T(t)) + 1)} + k \right) M(h, t) \quad (2.1)$$

for all $h, t \in X$ such that $\alpha_s(h, t) \geq c^2$ and $k \in [0, 1)$ where

$$M(h, t) = \left(d_{pb}^s(h, t) + d_{pb}^s(h, T(h)) + d_{pb}^s(t, T(t)) + \frac{d_{pb}^s(h, T(t)) + d_{pb}^s(t, T(h))}{2c} \right)$$

Assume that

a. There is $h_0 \in X$ such that $\alpha_s(h_0, T(h_0)) \geq c^2$ and

$$\frac{d_{pb}^s(h_0, T(h_0)) + d_{pb}^s(T(h_0), T^2(h_0))}{1 + d_{pb}^s(h_0, T(h_0)) + d_{pb}^s(T(h_0), T^2(h_0))} + k < \frac{1}{c} \quad (2.2)$$

b. X is α_s -regular.

Then T has at least one fixed point in X .

Proof:

By assumptions (a) there exists $h_0 \in X$ such that $\alpha_s(h_0, T(h_0)) \geq c^2$ and the above definition holds. Define a sequence $\{h_n\}$ by $h_n = T(h_{n-1}) = T^n(h_0)$ for all $n \geq 1$ since T is an α_s -orbital admissible map. Thus $\alpha_s(T(h_0), T^2(h_0)) \geq c^2$ by repeated application of α_s -orbital admissibility of map T we have for all $n \geq 0$

$$\alpha_s(h_n, h_{n+1}) = \alpha_s(T^n(h_0), T^{n+1}(h_0)) \geq c^2$$

Since $\alpha_s(h_n, h_{n+1}) \geq c^2$ for all $n \geq 0$, thus

$$d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) \leq d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n)$$

for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we note that,

$$\begin{aligned} & M(h_{n-1}, h_n) \\ &= \left\{ d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n), d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n), d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}), \frac{d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_{n+1}) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_n)}{2c}, \right. \\ & \quad \left. \frac{d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_{n+1}) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_n)}{2c} \right\} \\ &= \{ d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) \} \end{aligned}$$

If $M(h_{n-1}, h_n) = d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1})$, then by substitution $h = h_{n-1}$ and $t = h_n$ in the above definition, we get a contradiction. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) &\leq \left(\frac{d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_{n+1}) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_n)}{c(d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) + 1)} + k \right) d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n) \\ &\leq \left(\frac{d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1})}{c(d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) + 1)} + k \right) d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n) \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

Using the lemma (1.1.24), we know that the sequence

$$\left\{ \frac{d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1})}{c(d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) + 1)} \right\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$$

is non-increasing sequence. Consequently

$$\frac{d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1})}{c(d_{pb}^s(h_{n-1}, h_n) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) + 1)} \leq \frac{d_{pb}^s(h_0, h_1) + d_{pb}^s(h_1, h_2)}{c(d_{pb}^s(h_0, h_1) + d_{pb}^s(h_1, h_2) + 1)}$$

Let $\delta = \frac{d_{pb}^s(h_0, h_1) + d_{pb}^s(h_1, h_2)}{c(d_{pb}^s(h_0, h_1) + d_{pb}^s(h_1, h_2) + 1)} + k$ by (2.3) we obtain

$$d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) \leq \delta^n d_{pb}^s(h_0, h_1) \quad (2.4)$$

for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, by triangular inequality for $m \geq n$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_m) &\leq c \left(d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) + d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_m) \right) - d_{pb}^s(h_{n+1}, h_{n+1}) \\ &\leq c d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) + c^2 \left(d_{pb}^s(h_{n+1}, h_{n+2}) + d_{pb}^s(h_{n+2}, h_m) \right) - c d_{pb}^s(h_{n+2}, h_{n+2}) \\ &\leq c d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) + c^2 d_{pb}^s(h_{n+1}, h_{n+2}) + c^3 \left(d_{pb}^s(h_{n+2}, h_{n+3}) + d_{pb}^s(h_{n+3}, h_m) \right) \\ &\quad - c^2 d_{pb}^s(h_{n+3}, h_{n+3}) \\ &\leq c d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) + c^2 d_{pb}^s(h_{n+1}, h_{n+2}) + c^3 d_{pb}^s(h_{n+2}, h_{n+3}) + \dots + c^{m-n} d_{pb}^s(h_{m-1}, h_m) \end{aligned}$$

By inequality (2.1) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_m) &\leq c \delta^n d_{pb}^s(h_0, h_1) + c^2 \delta^{n+1} d_{pb}^s(h_0, h_1) \\ &\quad + c^3 \delta^{n+3} d_{pb}^s(h_0, h_1) + \dots + c^{m-n} \delta^{m-n} d_{pb}^s(h_0, h_1) \\ &\leq c \delta^n (1 + c\delta + (c\delta)^2 + \dots + (c\delta)^{m-n-1}) d_{pb}^s(h_0, h_1) \\ &\leq \frac{c\delta^n}{1 - c\delta} d_{pb}^s(h_0, h_1) \end{aligned}$$

Since $\delta \in [0, 1/c]$ and $c > 1$, thus

$$d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_m) = 0 \quad (2.5)$$

Hence h_n is a Cauchy Sequence in (X, d_{pb}^s, c) . Since (X, d_{pb}^s, c) is a complete partial b -metric space therefore by lemma (1.1.17)3 there exists $h^* \in X$ (say) such that

$$d_{pb}^s(h_n, h^*) = 0$$

If and only if

$$d_{pb}^s(h_n, h^*) = d_{pb}^s(h^*, h^*) = d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_m) \quad (2.6)$$

By (2.5) and (2.6), we have,

$$d_{pb}^s(h_n, h^*) = d_{pb}^s(h^*, h^*) = 0$$

Implies that $h_n d_{pb}^s \rightarrow h^*$.

Since $\alpha_s(h_n, h_{n+1}) \geq c^2$ and $h_n d_{pb}^s \rightarrow h^*$ by assumption (b), we have $\alpha_s(h_n, h^*) \geq c^2$. By contractive condition (2.1), we have

$$d_{pb}^s(h_{n+1}, T(h^*)) \leq \left(\frac{d_{pb}^s(h_n, T(h^*)) + d_{pb}^s(h^*, h_{n+1})}{c(d_{pb}^s(h_n, h_{n+1}) + d_{pb}^s(h^* + T(h^*)) + 1)} + k \right) M(h_n, h^*)$$

Taking limit $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have

$$d_{pb}^s(h^*, T(h^*)) \leq \left(\frac{d_{pb}^s(h^*, T(h^*))}{c(d_{pb}^s(h^* + T(h^*)) + 1)} + k \right) d_{pb}^s(h^*, T(h^*))$$

Hence by axiom $d_{pb}^s(1)$ and $d_{pb}^s(2)$ we get $h^* = T(h^*)$ which shows that h^* is a fixed point of T .

Remark:

Let T satisfy the conditions of Theorem (2.2). If h^* and t^* are two distinct fixed point of T satisfying, $\mathbb{Q}_s(h^*, t^*) \geq c^2$ then

$$d_{pb}^s(h^*, t^*) \geq \frac{c(1-k)}{2}$$

Proof:

We have proved that collection of fixed points of T is non-empty. Let h^* and t^* be two distinct fixed point of T . By contractive condition of theorem (2.1) we have

$$d_{pb}^s(T(h^*), T(t^*)) \leq \left(\frac{d_{pb}^s(h^*, T(t^*)) + d_{pb}^s(t^*, T(h^*))}{c(d_{pb}^s(h^*, T(h^*)) + d_{pb}^s(t^*, T(t^*)) + 1)} + k \right) M(h^*, t^*)$$

As $M(h^*, t^*) = d_{pb}^s(h^*, t^*)$

$$d_{pb}^s(h^*, t^*) \leq \left(\frac{d_{pb}^s(h^*, t^*) + d_{pb}^s(t^*, h^*)}{c(d_{pb}^s(h^*, h^*) + d_{pb}^s(t^*, t^*) + 1)} + k \right) d_{pb}^s(h^*, t^*)$$

So,

$$\frac{c(1-k)}{2} \leq d_{pb}^s(h^*, t^*)$$

The Example (2.3.1) illustrative theorem (2.1).

3. Application

Here, an application of result is presented showing the existence of every possible solution of boundary value problem given as:

$$\left\{ -\frac{d^s h}{d^s \zeta^2} = f(T, T(h)) \quad T \in [0,1] \quad h(0) = h(1) = 0 \text{ otherwise} \right. \quad (2.10)$$

here $f: [0,1] \times R \rightarrow R$ is a continuous and the associated green function is defined as:

$$G(T, R) = \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\zeta(1-\tau) \quad 0 \leq \zeta \leq \tau \leq 1 \\ &\tau(1-\zeta) \quad 0 \leq \tau \leq \zeta \leq 1 \end{aligned} \right.$$

Let the collection of all continuous mappings is denoted by $C[0,1]$ i.e. let $X = (C[0,1], R)$.

Define $d_{pb}^s: X \times X \rightarrow R_0^+$ by

$$d_{pb}^s(h, t) = \|(h - t)^2\|_\infty + \mu = \sup_{\zeta \in [0,1]} |T(h) - T(t)|^2 + \mu$$

where $\mu > 0$. Then (X, d_{pb}^s, c) is considered as complete partial b -metric space with $c = 2$.

Now define T as:

$$Th(\zeta) = \int_0^1 G(\zeta, \tau) f(\tau, h(\tau)) d\tau$$

for all $\zeta \in [0,1]$. Hence the given boundary value problem has a solution iff T has a fixed point.

4. Conclusion

The goal was to develop a class of non-expensive mappings known as $\mathbb{Q}_s$ -non-expensive mappings. These α_s -non-expensive mappings fully satisfied the generalized conditions of contraction. For demonstration of main results, few examples are provided. The application of proposed work is elaborated by applying it to a boundary value problem where the existence of solution is shown.

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